

Pollen-allergy in Pink City, Jaipur with Special Reference to Holoptelea Integrifolia: A Review

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Abstract

Pollen grains are minute biological particles, commonly referred to as "pollens," that are discharged by flowering plants during the process of pollination. Despite their microscopic size, these airborne biological particles contain certain proteins within their composition that can induce an allergic reaction upon contact with the human body. When Pollen Grain washed out by rainfall, pollen cytoplasmic granule are responsible for water soluble allergy. (Chakra *et al.*, 2011)

Pollens possess characteristics of being small, lightweight, and desiccated, enabling them to be transported over long distances through the air. Individuals who are genetically predisposed may experience allergies in response to the pollens released by certain grasses, trees, and weeds. However, it is worth noting that flowering plants such as roses and certain types of flowering trees typically do not provoke pollen allergies. In the city of Jaipur, pollen serves as a common trigger for seasonal allergies in both children and adults. Thus, a comprehensive review of the aeropalynological survey was undertaken in Jaipur from 2006 to March 2023. The presence of allergenic pollens in the air is discerned through the utilization of a specialized instrument known as the Burkard pollen counter. The installation of this device took place on the rooftop of the Asthma Bhawan, situated approximately 14 meters above ground level, specifically on the terrace of the Asthma Bhawan in Vidhyadhar Nagar, which is located in the north-western region of Jaipur.

Keywords Airborne Pollen, Bio particles, Aeropalynological, Aerospore.

Introduction

The most prevalent chronic condition worldwide is allergy, as stated in a study conducted by Singh and Mathur, (2013). The primary causes of pollen allergies are seasonal airborne particles, fungal spores, and dust mites, among others. (Singh ¹*et al.*, 2013) The focus of this review article is to emphasize the diverse aerobiological factors associated with these causative agents in the environment of Jaipur, commonly known as the "pink city." Allergenic disorders, such as bronchial asthma, allergic rhinitis, and atopic dermatitis, affect approximately 30% of the global population, as mentioned by Singh and Mathur, 2013 study.

Figure 1(Burkard)(installed at roof top of Asthma Bhawan, Jaipur)

Aim of study

The objective of this paper is to study Pollen-allergy in pink city, Jaipur with special reference to *Holoptelea Integrifola*: a review.

Review of Literature

In the recent years, the Covid-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on both human health and the environment, particularly in relation to air pollution and the anthropogenic causes of climate change. This complex and multifaceted crisis is undoubtedly one of the most pressing issues that the world is currently facing(M Bassiouni and K Taia, 2021). Within the context of this broader problem, it is particularly noteworthy to examine a specific case of pollen allergy in Jaipur, a city known for its high prevalence of this condition. The allergenic properties of pollen grains derived from flowering plants have long been recognized as a key catalyst for a range of allergic reactions, with symptoms encompassing various respiratory disorders such as hay fever, asthma, allergic rhinitis, as well as ocular manifestations like redness in the eyes and conjunctivitis. Additionally, individuals affected by this allergy often experience frequent bouts of sneezing and encounter difficulties in breathing, further exacerbating their discomfort and distress. (**Pollen Count, 2023**)(https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pollen_count)

Airborne pollen not only has the capability to induce allergic reactions, but fungal spores also have this potential, as highlighted by the research conducted by(M Bassiouni and K Taia, 2021). These microscopic grains of pollen are characterized by their small and minuscule size.(Prochaskaand Benowitz, 2016) Typically, the height of the pollen season persists until the conclusion of April, resulting in patients seeking medical assistance at hospitals with a range of symptoms, including nasal watery discharge, respiratory difficulties, wheezing, burning and irritated eyes, as well as skin rashes. However, during the month of June, the prevalence of sandstorms poses a challenge in terms of identifying pollen due to the accumulation of sand on the slides. Despite this obstacle, researchers were able to successfully identify certain pollen samples. It was observed that the highest counts of pollen were recorded in the months of April and August, while the lowest count was observed in June due to the aforementioned sandstorms. The concentration and types of pollen grains vary across different seasons. Various factors such as geographical location, flowering season, wind direction, local vegetation, climatic conditions, and meteorological factors contribute to the variability in pollen count and contribution, as stated in the works of(A. B. Singh and Mathur, 2013) and (M Bassiouni and K Taia, 2021). Within urban areas, the majority of pollen grains are produced by trees found along roadsides. These road trees are often densely planted in residential areas, workplaces, and along travel routes. Consequently, pollen emerges as a prevalent trigger for seasonal allergies among both children and adults in Jaipur. In order to provide a comprehensive overview of the pollen distribution within Jaipur, an aeropalynological survey was conducted from 2006 to March 2023.

Allergic pollens can be detected in the atmosphere by means of a specialized instrument called the Burkard pollen counter, which is widely used for this purpose. The analysis of different types of pollen and their respective seasons is of great benefit to clinicians, as well as to individuals suffering from allergies and tourists visiting the area. Specifically, it allows them to plan their trips accordingly and reduce the likelihood of experiencing allergic reactions. Jaipur, also known as the "Pink City" or "Gulabi Nagar" due to its distinctive architecture, is a highly sought-after destination for tourists from around the

world. Many people from various regions of India, as well as foreign visitors, are drawn to this city's unique charm and cultural heritage. Consequently, having access to information about the prevalence of allergens in the environment enables individuals to make informed decisions regarding their travel plans and take necessary precautions to mitigate the risk of allergic reactions. The quantification of pollen particles in the air can be achieved by utilizing specialized equipment called the Burkard Pollen Counter. This instrument is installed on the rooftop of the Asthma Bhawan, which is situated in Vidhyadhar Nagar, a northwestern neighborhood of Jaipur. (<https://asthmabhawan.com/pollen-watch/>) The device is strategically positioned approximately 14 meters above ground level, on the terrace of the Asthma Bhawan, to ensure accurate measurements. By employing a suction mechanism, the Burkard Pollen Counter is able to capture environmental air samples, effectively trapping the pollen particles within the equipment. Subsequently, these trapped particles can be examined and identified under a microscope, allowing for the determination of their quantity and specific type. The Burkard slide sampler is a compact, battery-operated device that uses a microlide coated with glycerine jelly to absorb air particles, impact them on a slide, and scan for pollen grains/fungal spore count. The prevalence of allergic diseases has been steadily increasing on a global scale. Environmental pollens, in particular, play a significant role in triggering conditions such as asthma, rhinitis, and conjunctivitis. It is typically observed that the symptoms of these diseases worsen during the pollination season of the plant species responsible for the release of the allergenic pollen. This is due to the fact that flowering plants tend to produce and disperse their pollen within a specific season, with the air carrying it to nearby areas. For individuals who are sensitive to these pollens, exposure can lead to the development of asthma and other allergic reactions. Consequently, regular monitoring of pollen levels can provide invaluable support to patients suffering from asthma and allergies. By keeping track of the pollen count, timely warnings can be issued to individuals, thus enabling them to take appropriate measures to prevent exacerbations of their allergies and asthma. The numerical value provided in the reports represents the quantity of pollen particles detected within a cubic meter of air over a period of 24 hours. The most prevalent airborne pollen allergens identified include Poaceae, Chino-Amaranthus, Asteraceae, Holoptelea, Cassia Spp., Brassica, Azadirachta, Parthenium, and various types of fungal spores. Interestingly, the highest pollen count tends to occur in the month of August, while the lowest count is typically observed in June. Fungal spores are particularly problematic for individuals with asthma, as they serve as a major source of contaminants. Moreover, even dead spores can contain allergenic substances, which can elicit allergic reactions and contribute to the development of conditions such as cardiac disease, dermatitis, and respiratory disorders. Among the various clinical presentations associated with these allergens, airborne contact dermatitis is the most commonly observed in individuals sensitive to parthenium. The objective of this review is to provide physicians with useful data pertaining to the prevalence of pollen allergens throughout the different months of the year. This information can greatly assist in the accurate diagnosis and effective treatment of patients suffering from allergies. In conclusion, it is evident from this study that allergic patients should avoid outdoor activities, such as walking, particularly early in the morning after 6 AM. These findings are of great relevance to physicians, as they can utilize this data to enhance the care provided to their allergy patients.

Methodology

The present review is based on an analysis of papers published in various journals, surveyed using the Burkard pollen counter and a variety of newspapers over eighteen years, from 2006 to 2023. (Chaurasia, 2021; Adhikari *et al.*, 2004; Singh¹ *et al.*, 2013; Chakra *et al.*, 2011; A. B. Singh and Mathur, 2013)

The current review, which aims to provide a comprehensive analysis and assessment, is grounded upon a meticulous examination and evaluation of a multitude of scholarly articles and papers that have been disseminated and made available in an assortment of esteemed and reputable academic journals. This exhaustive survey, encompassing a considerable timeframe spanning a total of eighteen years, specifically from 2006 to 2023, was conducted utilizing a highly reliable and extensively utilized instrument known as the Burkard pollen counter, which has been widely recognized and endorsed for its accuracy and precision in the measurement and quantification of pollen particles. Additionally, in order to ensure a comprehensive and well-rounded examination of the subject matter, various reputable and widely circulated newspapers were also meticulously scrutinized and incorporated into the research process. The combination of these scholarly sources and journalistic outlets contributes to the robustness and comprehensiveness of the analysis, thereby enhancing the reliability and validity of the findings and conclusions drawn from this review.

Pollen Count

The quantification of the quantity of grass, tree, fungal spores, and weeds in a specified volume of air that are widespread in the corresponding vicinity is conducted through the

assessment of pollen grain numbers. This assessment is usually expressed using a numerical scale ranging from 0 to 12, as illustrated in Table 1.

Table -1

(Singh¹et al., 2013; Chaurasia, 2021; https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pollen_count, n.d.)

Pollen Count	Pollen Level
0-2.4	Low
2.5-4.8	Low-Medium
4.9-7.2	Medium
7.3-9.6	High-Medium
9.7-12	High

Table -2

(Singh¹et al., 2013; Chaurasia, 2021; https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pollen_count, n.d.)

Grass		Tree		Weed		Fungal spore	
No of Pollen spore	Pollen Level	No of Pollen spore	Pollen Level	No of Pollen spore	Pollen Level	No of Pollen spore	Pollen Level
0	Absent	0	Absent	0	Absent	0	Absent
1-4	Low	1-14	Low	1-9	Low	1-6499	Low
5-19	Moderate	15-89	Moderate	10-49	Moderate	6500-12999	Moderate
20-199	High	90-1499	High	50-499	High	13000-49999	High
>200	Very High	>1500	Very High	>500	Very High	>50000	Very High

Result and Discussion

Allergic rhinitis induced by exposure to pollen is one of the most prevalent allergic disorders. The inhalation of airborne pollen is a significant catalyst for an allergic reaction or hay fever. (Prochaska and Benowitz, 2016) Pollen, which is a fine yellowish powder responsible for the fertilization of other plants, is dispersed by the wind, birds, insects, or other animals. Pollen plays an exceedingly crucial role in the growth of plants and its concentration is particularly elevated during the spring and summer seasons, which are commonly known as the pollen allergy season. Due to its extensive distribution, pollen allergy ranks among the most prevalent outdoor allergies worldwide. (Shriram and Malladi, 2020) In fact, one out of every seven individuals globally experiences a pollen allergy. While some individuals suffer from pollen allergies throughout the year, others are only triggered during specific periods, mainly during the pollen season. Pollens are predominantly released by a specific tree at the onset of spring in Jaipur. Allergy and asthma patients in Jaipur face considerable difficulties from February to April. The transition of seasons during this period becomes an annual ordeal of suffering. The augmented presence of pollen from the *Holoptelea integrifolia* tree in the atmosphere leads to allergic reactions among the population in Jaipur. The research division of the Asthma department in Jaipur has implemented a device that registers high pollen levels in the air during this time frame. Increased sensitivity is observed among individuals in the city towards the end of the winter season. Symptoms such as sneezing, redness of the eyes, and nasal congestion have been reported as a result of pollen allergies.

According to a study conducted by (Singh et al., 2013; Chaurasia, 2021) aeroallergens play a significant role in respiratory allergy conditions such as asthma and allergic rhinitis, particularly those originating from the plant *Holoptelea integrifolia*. In a research conducted in Jaipur, a single intra-day pattern of pollen was discovered, with the lowest count occurring between 4-6 AM and the highest concentration occurring between 2-4 PM. The amount of pollen present throughout the day is twice as high as it is from 8 PM to 6 AM. Armed with this knowledge, healthcare professionals and individuals with allergies can take measures to avoid exposure to these elements during the daytime (Singh et al., 2013 and D. Singh et al., 2013)

Singh et al. conducted a study in 2013 to investigate the role of air-borne pollen in allergic conditions such as asthma and rhinitis. They discovered a total of 41 common pollen types, predominantly originating from anemophilous trees and grasses, through their research conducted in Jaipur. The pollen season extended from July to October

and March to April, with the highest concentrations occurring in August. Notable contributors to the pollen count included Poaceae, Chenoamaranthus, Asteraceae, Holoptelea, Cassia Spp., Brassica, Azadiracta, and Parthenium.(Singh *et al.*, 2013)

Kapyal (1984) conducted a study on the impact of pollen allergies on human health, focusing on different concentrations of fallen pollen from various species. Increasing the temperature and decreasing of relativity humidity were closely related with increasing the pollen court.

According to the research conducted by Norris Hill in 1991, there exists a correlation between the subjective concept of relative humanity and the impact of the pollen count in the Earth's atmosphere.

The study conducted by Spie.

Isma in 1983 observed that there were daily variations in [something] as a result of changes in wind direction and the occurrence of precipitation.

in a separate investigation, as stated by Berggren et al in 1995, the impact of precipitation on the quantity of pollen surpasses that of temperature, relative humidity, and wind direction.

In the investigation conducted by Dimple Singh in 2013, it was discovered that a solitary intraduranal pattern exhibited the minimum quantity of pollen between the hours of 4 and 6 in the morning, while the highest quantity of pollen was observed between 2 and 4 in the afternoon for the pollen of *Holoptelea integrifolia* in the urban area known as the pink city, Jaipur.

Several studies conducted by researchers such as Kapylaet *al.*, (1984), Kuohet *al.* (1999), Raynoet *al.*, (1971), and Norris-Hill *et al.*, (1991) have documented the prevalence of specific types of airborne pollen taxa within the spectrum.

***Holoptelea integrifolia*:-**

Holoptelea integrifolia, a member of the Ulmaceae family, is the sole species present in India within deciduous regions (Sharma and Singh, 2012) The flowering period of *Holoptelea integrifolia* spans from mid-February to the conclusion of March [8]. This particular tree, *Holoptelea integrifolia*, is a significant contributor to pollen allergies in Jaipur, Delhi, and the National Capital Region (NCR), as well as other areas in North India.(***Holoptelea integrifolia Tree | the Cause of Pollen Allergy in Jaipur?*, 2016**)

Individuals who suffer from both allergic rhinitis and asthma are significantly impacted by the rise in pollen levels that occur during the spring season. This particular type of plant is frequently encountered in public parks, along the city's roadsides, as well as in prominent locations such as Central Park, Gandhi Nagar, and Vaishali Nagar, where individuals often engage in morning walks and subsequently suffer from health issues. (***Allergy Pollens Found in Air 1st Time This Season in Jaipur*, 2023**)

Individuals afflicted with allergic rhinitis and asthma should exercise caution in the presence of pollen from the *Holoptelea integrifolia* plant, commonly known as the "chilbil or bandarki roti tree". *Holoptelea integrifolia*, also referred to as the chilbil/Bandar Ki Roti, is a substantial deciduous tree that reaches heights of 20-25 meters. The bark of mature trees assumes a dull grey hue and peels away in corky scales. The flowers are diminutive and covered in fine hairs, exhibiting hues that span from deep green to dark brown. Flowering occurs during the months of January and February, while fruit-bearing transpires from March to May. The climatic conditions in Jaipur are conducive to the growth of *Holoptelea integrifolia*, and the nursery operated by the forest department plays a pivotal role in its propagation.(***Allergy Pollens Found in Air 1st Time This Season in Jaipur*, 2023**)

Holoptelea integrifolia, the plant known for its significant allergenic pollen production, was detected in the atmospheric environment of Jaipur on the twenty-fourth of February, 2023, marking the initial occurrence of this season. The density of *Holoptelea integrifolia* pollen particles in the atmosphere remains notably elevated for a duration ranging between one to two months. Notably, these pollen particles exhibit a higher presence during the morning and evening hours. It is important to note that the existence of this particular pollen in the air may pose adverse effects on individuals with susceptibility to allergies. (The Times of India, February 24, 2023).

Normally, the period of peak pollen occurrence typically persists until the conclusion of the month of April, leading to the arrival of patients at medical facilities displaying various symptoms, such as the discharge of watery nasal secretions, respiratory difficulties, wheezing, ocular irritation, and dermatological rashes. In Jaipur, an abundance of *Holoptelea* trees can be observed. The majority of individuals remain uninformed regarding the detrimental consequences stemming from these trees. These trees can commonly be found in government-maintained parks, Central Park, Gandhi Nagar, and Vaishali Nagar, which are popular destinations for early morning strolls, unfortunately resulting in a substantial number of individuals falling ill. Around 10% of individuals with asthma experience an allergic reaction to the *Holoptelea* plant, as reported by *The Times of India* in 2023. Those who possess sensitivities to this particular plant are advised to refrain from venturing outdoors and to diligently cover their nose and mouth with a triple-layered mask during the morning and evening hours. Experts have approximated that no less than 30% of the population in North India and 10% of the total population throughout India are afflicted by allergies, with 40-60% of airborne pollen originating from the *Holoptelea integrifolia* tree in Jaipur. This tree disperses a significant amount of pollen into the atmosphere during the months of January and February in comparison to other plants. These pollens are responsible for inducing various allergic reactions among the local inhabitants, including respiratory ailments such as asthma, allergies, rhinitis, ocular redness, conjunctivitis, nasal congestion, sneezing, and breathing difficulties.

Figure 3 (shows the green-coloured cluster of unripe fruit)
The above picture of the *Holoptelea integrifolia* tree shows the green-coloured cluster is its unripe fruit. Here is a picture of its fruit before it turns brown.

Figure 2 (pollen allergic agent of different families) (<https://asthmabhawan.com/pollen-watch/>, (n.d.), Asthma Bhawan. <https://asthmabhawan.com/pollen-watch/>)

Table -3 (Common allergic plants of different seasons)(A. B. Singh and Mathur, 2013 and N. Singh *et al.*, 2017)

Plant	Spring(Feb.-Apr.)	Autumn(Sep.-Oct.)	Winter(Nov.-Jan.)	Throughout year
Tree	Pithecellobium-dulce	Neriumindicum	Acacia spp.	
	Azadiractaindica		Albizzialebeck	
	Bauhinia		Callistenon	
	Cassia.sp.			
	Parkinsoniaaculeata			
	Buteamonosperma			

	Delonixregia Callistenon Dalbergia Riccinuscommunis Holopteleaintegrifolia Kigelia Tecomellaundulata Salvadorspersica			
Weed	Argemone		Ziziphusmauritiana	Parthenium
Grass		Tephrosias sp. Chenopod- Amaranthus	Asphodelous Ageratum Brassica spp. Chenopod- Amaranthus	Cyanodon Euphorbia- hirta

Table 4 (Common allergic plants of different seasons)(A. B. Singh and Mathur, 2013;Singh *et al.*, 2013;D. Singh *et al.*, 2013and N. Singh *et al.*, 2017)

Family	Name of plant which produced allergic pollen	Peak Concentration of pollen time
Mimosaceae	Acacia spp.	January -December
	Albizzialebeck	
	Pithecellobium-dulce	February -may
Asteraceae	Ageratum	Throughout year
Asteraceae	Parthenium	Throughout year
Papaveraceae	Argemone	November -May
Liliaceae	Asphodelous	December -March
Meliaceae	Azadiractaindica	March-June
Caeselpiniaceae	Bauhinia	February -March
	Cassia. sp.	Aprail-June
	Parkinsoniaaculeata	January-Aprail
Brassicaceae	Brassica spp.	November-February

	Buteamonosperma	March-Aprail
	Delonixregia	Feburary -March
Fabaceae	Tephrosias sp.	Augast-October
Myrtaceae	Callistenon	February-March and Oct. -November
Amaranthaceae	Chenopod-Amaranthus	July-November
Poaceae	Cyanodon	January- AprailandAugast- December
Papilionaceae	Dalbergia	Feburary -March
	Euphorbia-hirta	Throught the year
Euphorbiaceae	Riccinuscommunis	November-Aprail
Ulmaceae	Holopteleaintegrifolia	February-Aprail
	Kigelia	Aprail-June
Bignoniaceae	Tecomellaundulata	February-Aprail
Apocynaceae	Neriumindicum	Aprail-September
Salvadoracear	Salvadorspersica	
Rhamneaceae	Ziziphusmauritiana	September-December